

A GIS-Based Fuzzy AHP Approach for Seismic Network Station Placement

Antonio Brcković¹, Goran Čorak¹, Vedran Damjanović², Valentina Gašo¹, Stjepo Grljević³, Viktorija Milec¹, Bruno Mravlja¹, Marko Kapelj¹, Iva Kostanjšek¹, Marko Pervan¹, Anamarija Tremljan Milun¹, Tomislav Fiket^{1,*}

¹ University of Zagreb, Faculty of Science, Geophysical Department, Croatian Seismological Survey, Zagreb, Croatia, antonio.brckovic@gfz.hr, goran.corak@gfz.hr, valentina.gaso@gfz.hr, viktorija.milec@gfz.hr, bruno.mravlja@gfz.hr, marko.kapelj@gfz.hr, iva.kostanjsek@gfz.hr, marko.pervan@gfz.hr, anamarija.tremljan.milun@gfz.hr, tomislav.fiket@gfz.hr

² TerraSens, Vrbovec, Croatia, vedran.damjanovic@terrasens.hr

³ Jan De Nul Group, Hofstade Aalst, Belgium, s.grljevic@gmail.com

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The optimal placement of seismic network stations is crucial for enhancing detection capability, improving data quality, and refining seismic hazard assessment. Station siting involves multiple, often conflicting criteria related to environmental conditions, anthropogenic noise sources, geological suitability, and logistical constraints. This study presents a GIS-based multicriteria decision-making framework integrating the Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy AHP) to determine suitable locations for seismic station placement. A comprehensive set of spatial criteria was considered, including geological characteristics, hydrological conditions, land cover and forest distribution, proximity to industrial zones, traffic density, transportation infrastructure, and other environmental and anthropogenic factors affecting seismic noise and site stability. Fuzzy AHP was employed to address uncertainty and subjectivity in expert judgments during the criteria-weighting process, enabling more flexible and realistic pairwise comparisons. The weighted criteria were integrated within a GIS environment to generate a spatial suitability map identifying suitable zones for station installation. The results demonstrate that integrating fuzzy-based multicriteria evaluation with spatial analysis significantly enhances decision support for seismic network design. The proposed approach provides a systematic, transparent, and adaptable framework that can be applied to both regional and national-scale seismic network planning.

Keywords: seismic network design; GIS; Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA); Fuzzy AHP; seismic noise.

1 Introduction

The Republic of Croatia is a moderately seismically active region, as demonstrated by the devastating earthquakes in Zagreb and Petrinja in 2020 (Markušić et al. 2020, Markušić et al. 2021). These events highlighted the limitations of the existing national seismic network, especially in terms of station density and spatial coverage (Trnkoczy 2002). As part of the modernization efforts through the CROSSNET project, the development of a dense and efficient seismic network required a systematic approach to station location (Ringler et al. 2022, Kring et al. 2014). The process of selecting suitable locations is a complex task that involves multiple, often conflicting criteria, such as geological

conditions, environmental noise sources, accessibility and infrastructure constraints (Bormann et al. 2013, Lee et al., 1981). Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA), combined with geographic information systems (GIS), provided a robust framework for addressing such problems (Qaddah et al. 2017, Qaddah et al. 2018, Messaoudi et al. 2019). In particular, the Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy AHP) allows for the inclusion of uncertainty and expert judgment in the weighting criteria (Fu 2020). This study presents a GIS-based MCDA framework for seismic station location selection, with a focus on the development of the methodology and initial results. A comprehensive evaluation and validation of the approach will be addressed in a subsequent paper.

2 Materials and methods

The study area encompasses the Republic of Croatia, which is characterized by diverse geological and geomorphological conditions, ranging from the Pannonian Basin to the Dinaric karst region (Velić et al. 2009, HGI 2009). The country experiences moderate seismicity with spatially variable earthquake occurrence (Ivančić et al. 2018). Owing to its elongated shape and complex terrain, designing a seismic network requires careful spatial optimization to ensure adequate coverage and minimize detection gaps (Antonovskaya et al. 2017). The territory of the Republic of Croatia was divided into 95 Thiessen (Voronoi) polygons (Okabe 2000), generated from an initial set of points corresponding to the planned number of seismic stations (Figure 1).

The methodology combines GIS-based spatial analysis with Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) using Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy AHP). The workflow consisted of three main steps, namely the classification of input criteria, the spatial processing and transformation of data, and their integration through a weighted overlay approach. The input criteria were divided into three groups. Buffer criteria represent sources of seismic noise, such as roads, industrial zones, and power plants, where suitability increases with distance. Excluded criteria represent restricted areas, including flood zones and protected zones, where station installation is not feasible. Classified criteria describe intrinsic site properties, such as geology, slope, morphology, and insolation, which directly influence site suitability. A total of more than 70 criteria

Figure 1. Thiessen (Voronoi) polygons used as a spatial framework for the design of the future seismic network.

Figure 2. Flowchart for seismic station placement derived using GIS-based multicriteria analysis.

were considered, including over 30 buffer, more than 40 classified criteria and two excluded criteria. The large number of criteria reflects the need to capture the complexity of environmental, geological, and anthropogenic factors influencing seismic station performance. Buffer criteria were processed using distance-based functions and transformed into suitability values using fuzzy membership functions. Excluded areas were masked from further analysis. Classified criteria were discretized into classes and assigned suitability scores based on expert knowledge and literature. The relative importance of criteria was determined using the Fuzzy AHP

method, which allows pairwise comparison under uncertainty. The resulting weights were used to combine individual raster layers into a final suitability map. Figure 2. is showing the flowchart of the process applied.

3 Results

The application of the proposed methodology resulted in a spatial suitability map identifying areas with varying levels of suitability for seismic station installation. Karlovac County was used as a representative example of the applied methodology in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Suitability map for seismic station placement in Karlovac County derived using GIS-based multicriteria analysis.

The analysis demonstrated that the integration of multiple spatial criteria significantly reduces the potential area for station placement, highlighting only a limited subset of locations with suitable conditions. The applied constraints resulted in very few highly suitable locations, representing well below 1% of the total area (Table 1). These locations appear as spatially discrete and fragmented patches distributed across the study area, rather than forming continuous zones. Most of the territory was classified as unsuitable or excluded, indicating that a large proportion of the area is affected by limiting factors such as proximity to anthropogenic noise sources, unfavorable geological conditions, or restricted zones. Areas classified as suitable were more widespread but remain discontinuous, forming transitional zones between unsuitable and highly suitable locations. The highest suitability classes were generally observed in areas that are spatially separated from major infrastructure and densely developed regions. At the same time, these areas were not entirely remote, as suitable zones still occur in locations with sufficient access. The resulting spatial pattern was characterized by strong

heterogeneity, with suitability varying significantly over relatively short distances. These patterns were consistent within the analyzed area and indicate a stable spatial response of the applied criteria.

Table 1. Summary statistics of seismic station suitability classes for the Republic of Croatia.

Suitability class	Area (km ²)	Area (%)	Spatial characteristics
Excluded / unsuitable	40679.96	70.32	Continuous dominant areas
Transitional / less suitable	16567.77	28.64	Discontinuous transitional zones
Suitable / highly suitable	603.93	1.04	Fragmented isolated patches

4 Discussion

The proposed framework enables the integration of diverse spatial criteria within a consistent and reproducible approach, allowing complex environmental and anthropogenic constraints to be evaluated simultaneously. The results demonstrate that the application of multiple criteria leads to a strong spatial reduction of candidate areas, highlighting that only a limited portion of the territory meets the conditions required for suitable station placement. This confirms the necessity of a structured and data-driven approach, as simple geometric or uniform network configurations do not adequately account for spatial variability in site conditions. At the same time, the results emphasize that the highest suitability values identified by the model represent theoretical optima, which must be balanced against practical constraints. Accessibility is a key factor, as the installation and maintenance of seismic stations require reliable access for personnel and equipment. In this context, proximity to road infrastructure represents an important advantage, even if it may slightly reduce the theoretical suitability of a location. Similarly, logistical considerations, including the duration and efficiency of field surveys, favor sites that are not excessively remote. Additional factors, such as the risk of vandalism or theft, further influence site selection, and in some cases locations with occasional human presence may represent a more robust choice despite not being optimal in purely spatial terms. Furthermore, certain factors, such as the extent and evolution of urban areas, cannot be precisely defined within a static spatial framework, introducing additional uncertainty into the analysis. The results presented should therefore be interpreted as a first-order screening of potential locations rather than a final selection.

Described framework provides a systematic and flexible approach for seismic station siting, enabling the integration of heterogeneous spatial datasets and expert knowledge within a unified decision-making process. By combining multiple criteria within a GIS-based environment, the method allows for consistent evaluation

of spatial suitability across large and geologically diverse areas. A key advantage of the approach lies in its ability to account for competing constraints, particularly those related to anthropogenic noise, geological conditions, and accessibility. In contrast to purely geometric or uniform network design strategies, the presented method incorporates spatial variability in site conditions, allowing for the identification of locally suitable locations within a broader network configuration. However, the current approach relies on spatial proxies to represent seismic noise and site quality, which introduces inherent limitations. While such proxies are necessary for large-scale screening, they cannot fully capture site-specific conditions, particularly those related to subsurface properties or temporal variability in noise levels. Consequently, the results should be interpreted as a first-order approximation of site suitability rather than a definitive selection of station locations. Direct validation through field-based measurements, such as ambient seismic noise analysis using PPSD and HVSR methods, is therefore essential to confirm the predicted suitability of selected sites. In addition, the influence of criteria weighting on the final results represents an important source of uncertainty. Although the Fuzzy AHP approach provides a structured way to incorporate expert judgment, variations in weighting schemes may lead to differences in the resulting suitability patterns. A systematic sensitivity analysis would be required to assess the robustness of the model. Finally, the presented framework is adaptable and can be extended by incorporating additional criteria or higher-resolution datasets, depending on data availability and specific network requirements. This flexibility makes it suitable not only for national-scale network planning but also for regional or local applications where more detailed analysis may be required.

5 Conclusions

The aim of this study was to develop a methodology for the selection of suitable sites for seismic stations using GIS-based modeling in combination with multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA), with particular emphasis on the Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process. Overall, the proposed methodology provides an effective tool for reducing large candidate areas and supporting the initial phase of seismic network design, while significantly narrowing the scope of subsequent field investigations. Future work will focus on field validation using ambient seismic noise measurements, sensitivity analysis of criteria weighting, and integration with seismic network performance metrics, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of network efficiency and detection capability.

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6 References

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